

PROPERTIES OF CONCENTRATED SOLUTION OF ARABIC ACID AND THE INFLUENCE OF TEMPERATURE ON SOME OF THESE

BY S. N. MUKHERJEE AND AMULYA CHARAN BHOWMIK

Variations of specific conductance and hydrogen-ion activity in a concentrated solution of arabic acid follow the same sequence as in dilute solutions. Variations in refractive index, extinction coefficient, specific rotation and relative viscosity with concentration show breaks which do not occur at the same point for the different properties. In understanding the influence of temperature on relative viscosity and specific conductance the role of hydration and aggregate formation should also be taken into consideration, over and above the influence of the changes in ionic mobility and dielectric constant.

In a previous communication (Mukherjee and Ghosh, *this Journal*, 1949, 26, 81) variations of some physical and electrochemical properties of arabic acid solution with concentration have been reported. Results so far obtained tend to indicate the formation of aggregates probably from very low concentrations. But only dilute solutions were studied therein, the uppermost concentrations being in the neighbourhood of 2 g. of the acid per litre of the solution. Arabic acid is, however, miscible with water to form a colloidal solution almost in any proportion. In the present communication physical and electrochemical properties have been studied with reference to their variations with concentration of the solution and to the effect of temperature on some of them in concentrated solutions, up to above 95 g. of the acid per litre of the solution. A few more physical properties like refractive index, relative viscosity, extinction coefficient etc. have also been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

The method of preparation, purification and dissolution of the acid in water to form a colloidal solution have been the same as reported in the paper referred to above (Mukherjee and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). An examination of the keeping properties of the solutions revealed that a concentrated solution can be preserved much longer than a dilute one without any signs of change in the general appearance or of any physical properties as studied herein. Reproducibility of the different samples of the solutions, which were prepared in this connection, was also tested and found to be satisfactory in the sense that with the same acid concentration, the p_H and the specific conductance were within limits of experimental accuracy.

DISCUSSION

Specific Conductance and Hydrogen-ion Activity.—Data for the variation of these properties have been presented in Table I. Variations of the total acidity (C_N) shown in column 4 and calculated from potentiometric titrations of the acid with NaOH indicate a strict proportionality of this quantity with concentration, and therefore warrant the conclusion that the total acidity per g. of the acid does not change, even in a concentrated solution.

TABLE I

Temp. = $35^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. Sp. cond. of water used = 1.2×10^{-6} mho at 35° .

Conc. (g./l).	p_H	$a_H \times 10^4 N$	$c_H \times 10^4 N$	a_H/c_H ratio	Sp. cond. obs. $\times 10^4$	Equiv. cond per g./l.
3.0	3.21	6.17	28.7	0.215	1.68	0.56×10^{-1}
5.0	3.09	8.18	57.5	0.142	2.74	0.41
12.0	3.04	9.12	112.0	0.081	5.35	0.44
24.0	2.81	15.49	225.3	0.070	8.82	0.37
48.6	2.48	33.11	460.0	0.072	14.42	0.30
60.9	2.35	44.65	557.3	0.080	17.60	0.39
81.0	2.08	83.65	780.0	0.107	20.32	0.23
96.0	1.96	109.60	890.5	0.129	21.53	0.22

There is, however, no point of any special interest in the variations of the other properties, the changes all appearing to follow the sequence of the more dilute solutions, as reported before, excepting in the case of a_H/c_H ratio where there appears a minimum at a concentration of 24 g. per litre, beyond which there is a tendency for the value of this ratio to increase. There is no evidence for the appearance of a minimum in the $\Lambda - \sqrt{c}$ curve, where Λ represents equivalent conductance on the basis of 1 g. of the acid as its equivalent weight.*

Refractive Index.—Variation of refractive index with concentration as studied with the help of an Abbe refractometer has been shown in column 2 of Table II.

TABLE II

Temp. = 30°

Conc. (g./l.)	Ref. index.	Sp. rotation.	Conc. (g./l.)	Ref. index.	Sp. rotation.
0.30	1.3325	26.66	4.90	1.3382	21.66
0.60	1.3329	25.00	6.10	1.3395	21.46
1.20	1.3336	24.70	7.30	1.3414	20.60
2.45	1.3352	22.60	8.50	1.3428	22.20
			9.60	1.3446	22.80

The nature of the variations has been graphically shown in Fig. 1. The graph is almost linear and shows a well defined break at a concentration of about 0.9 g. of the acid per litre. This point fairly agrees with the concentration at which the $\Lambda - \sqrt{c}$ curve shows a break, as reported by Mukherjee and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*).

* Since the total acidity of this acid has been observed to vary with the nature of the base used for titration (to be discussed in a subsequent communication) this arbitrary value of equivalent conductance, which is strictly proportional to the true value, has been adopted.

Specific Rotation.—These data have been calculated for 1 g. of the acid per c.c. of the solution at 30° and presented in column 3, Table II. These values of $[\alpha]_D^{30}$ tend at first to diminish with concentration and show minimum at a concentration of about 7.3 g. per litre, which is much higher than those where inflexion points have been observed in some of the other properties studied (*vide supra*). The increase of $[\alpha]_D^{30}$ beyond the minimum is, however, small. The tendency for a minimum may be attributed to one or both of the factors mentioned below: (i) diminution of the number of optically active particles per unit volume of the solution, and (ii) internal compensation.

FIG. 1

FIG. 3

FIG. 2

FIG. 4

The first of these possibilities does not seem to hold since with increasing concentration the number of optically active bodies cannot diminish. As to the second possibility, viz. that of internal compensation, it is difficult, *a priori*, to come to any definite conclusions. If, however, a progressive aggregate formation be assumed, such a diminution, as observed herein, is not altogether impossible and in this respect it lends some support to the hypothesis of aggregate formation in this case.

Absorption and Extinction Coefficient.—Results of absorption measurements at different wave-lengths in the visible region, as observed in a spectrophotometer (König-Maitens type, have been presented graphically in Fig. 2 at three different concentrations by plotting the extinction coefficient ($\log I_0/I$) against λ in Å, where I_0 and I stand for the intensities of the incident and transmitted radiations respectively. All the three curves show maxima which occur at different concentrations showing a tendency to shift towards shorter wave-lengths with increase in concentration.

The extinction coefficient (ϵ) calculated per g. of the acid also changes with concentration showing a minimum as shown in Fig. 3. The concentration corresponding to this minimum occurs at a region of about 1.5 g. per litre which, although not close, but is still in the neighbourhood of 1 g. approximately where some other properties have shown their breaks. Beyond the minimum the values of ϵ increase almost to a constant value at higher concentrations.

Relative Viscosity.—Relative viscosities as measured by an Ostwald viscometer at two different temperatures (35° and 45°) have been shown graphically in Fig. 4. The data shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Conc. (g./l).	Relative viscosity		Conc. (g./l).	Relative viscosity	
	at 35°.	at 45°.		at 35°.	at 45°.
0	1.0	1.0	4.60	2.40	2.
0.25	1.15	1.14	5.75	2.90	2.
0.57	1.25	1.20	6.70	3.40	3.
1.15	1.37	1.31	8.50	4.32	3.
2.30	1.67	1.60	9.20	5.12	4.

Viscosity at both the temperatures at first shows a small but almost linear increase with concentration but at higher concentrations the variations are more abrupt making the curves convex towards the concentration axis. One peculiar feature in these cases is that there is no sharp or abrupt break in the course of the curves anywhere. The curves do not run exactly parallel but tend to diverge more and more at higher concentrations.

Kruyt and Tendeloo (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1929, **29**, 396) as well as Taft and Long (J. Phys. Chem., 1931, **38**, 874) have regarded the mode of increase of relative viscosity at higher concentrations as, observed herein, as a characteristic feature of all lyophilic colloids. In support of this they have compared the mode of variation of viscosity of gelatin, a typical colloid, with concentration with that of cane sugar which is a crystalloid. The variation of viscosity in the present system is intermediate between these two extreme cases. These observations may probably be explained in the light of the discussions advanced by one of the authors (S. N. M.) to explain the viscosity of gum Jeol solutions (vide Mukherjee and Rohatgi, this *Journal*, 1948, **25**, 339).

Effect of Temperature on Relative Viscosity and Specific Conductance

(i) The relative viscosity at different temperatures have been determined for different concentrations, one containing 102 g. of the acid per litre and the

11.5 g./litre only. The changes have been graphically represented in Fig. 5. At lower temperatures relative viscosity changes very little in both the cases, but this region of slow change is subsequently followed by one of steep fall. The curve then runs almost flat over a certain temperature range beyond which there is again a downward course which runs almost linear. Both the curves are similar in their general appearance, the initial flat course being a little shorter for the more concentrated solution. The steeper slope of the curve for the more concentrated solution indicates a higher temperature coefficient, the average values being 1.25 and 0.28% for 10.2 and 1.15% solutions respectively within the range of temperature from 30° to 55°.

The marked fall in viscosity at higher temperatures may partly be attributed to the dehydrating tendency and partly to the tendency towards disintegration on the part of the micelles at higher temperatures. In the light of this it may be expected that the more concentrated solution will have a higher temperature coefficient, since in this case both the effects referred to above should be much more pronounced than in dilute solutions. This is borne out by observations.

(ii) As before, both the solutions referred to above have been used to study the effect of temperature on specific conductance and the results obtained have been shown in Table IV and in Fig. 6. In both cases there has been an increase of specific conductance with rise of temperature up to a certain limit and the temperature coefficient is higher for a concentrated solution than for a dilute one. In no case does it amount to 2% as in the case of common electrolytes. While the concentrated solution has a maximum of specific conductance at about 65° beyond which there is a tendency to decrease, the dilute solution appears to reach a constant maximum value and shows no decreasing tendency up to the temperature studied. Pauli and Ripper (*Kolloid Z.*, 1933, 62, 162)

FIG. 5

FIG. 6

also observed similar increase of sp. conductance with temperature in acidoid gum arabic solutions of different concentrations and explained their results as the outcome of two principal factors operating simultaneously. Firstly the mobility of the ions increases with rise of temperature and secondly they believe that the decrease of dielectric constant of the medium with increase of temperature increases the interionic forces and thus decreases the effective the degree of dissociation in consequence of which the number of carrier ions as also their specific conductance become less.

TABLE IV

Temp.	Sp. cond. in 10.2% soln.	mho $\times 10^4$ 1.15% soln.	Temp.	Sp. cond. in 10.2% soln.	mho $\times 10^4$ 1.15% soln.
0°	17.51	4.43	45°	28.09	7.00
5°	18.76	4.66	50°	28.49	7.12
10°	19.86	5.13	55°	28.82	7.30
15°	21.72	5.45	60°	29.21	7.38
20°	23.21	5.72	65°	29.21	7.35
25°	24.36	5.99	70°	28.82	7.33
30°	25.34	6.59	75°	29.01	7.33
35°	26.25	—	80°	28.62	7.33
40°	27.05	6.77	85°	28.36	7.34

TABLE V

Temp. range.	10.2% soln.	Temperature coefficients.	1.15% soln.
10°-20°	1.76		1.15
20°-30°	0.98		0.94
30°-40°	0.91		0.86
40°-50°	0.53		0.51
50°-60°	0.26		0.27

Pauli and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) have looked upon these systems as true electrolytic ones in which the Debye-Hückel interionic attraction theory is applicable. But whether changes in ionic mobility and dielectric constant are sufficient to account for the observed facts is still an open question. If we look upon the arabic acid solution as a common electrolytic system in which complete dissociation and interionic attraction prevail, then from Debye-Hückel-Onsagar equation the equivalent conductance would be given by the relation :

$$\Lambda_0 - \Lambda = \left[\frac{29.0 (Z_+ Z_-)}{(DT)^{0.5} \eta} + \frac{0.986 \times 10^6}{(DT)^{1.5}} \omega \Lambda_0 \right] \sqrt{2\mu}$$

where $\omega = Z_+ Z_- \frac{2q}{1 + \sqrt{q}}$ and $q = \frac{Z_+ Z_- (u_1 + u_2)}{(Z_+ + Z_-)(Z_+ u_1 + Z_- u_2)}$ and the other terms

have their usual significance.

$$\text{Whence } \Lambda = \Lambda_0 - \left[\frac{29.0 (Z_+ Z_-)}{(DT)^{0.5} \eta} + \frac{0.986 \times 10^6}{(DT)^{1.5}} \omega \Lambda_0 \right] \sqrt{2\mu}$$

With rise of temperature the dielectric constant of water D varies with temperature T in such a manner that their product remains approximately constant, which holds fairly well for dilute aqueous solutions as well. Again, whether the value of Λ_0 will remain constant, as the viscosity of the solution changes quite markedly with rise of temperature, is another problem, because by Walden's rule (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, 58, 207) the product of $\Lambda_0\eta$ remains approximately constant, independent of temperature. In the arabic acid solution a marked decrease in viscosity with temperature is likely to bring about a proportionate increase in Λ_0 , and hence the direction in which the net equivalent conductance of the solution will change in such a case cannot be ascertained *a priori*. Moreover, in this case hydration of micelles plays a considerable rôle and a gradual dehydration at higher temperature is expected to contribute to an increase in specific conductance due to diminution of particle size. If, however, the disintegration of the micelles at higher temperature be assumed in this case, which is not wholly unlikely, the valency of the anions, as it occurs in the above equation, will lose its significance and the diminution of particle size will increase anionic mobility. But such disintegration will involve a diminished charge density (cf. McBain, *loc. cit.*) which will again diminish the mobility leading to a decrease of specific conductance. All these factors acting simultaneously will affect the variation of specific conductance with temperature in a complex manner and the predominance of one or the other of these will ultimately determine the net result.

Temperature coefficients of specific conductance, calculated from the data in Table IV, have been presented in Table V for both the solutions referred to above. The more concentrated solution shows a slightly higher temperature coefficient at lower temperatures and the difference becomes less marked as the temperature rises. This fact also can also be understood in the light of the importance of the rôle of hydration and the degree of association in these systems.

The authors' grateful thanks are due to Dr. J. N. Mukherjee, D.Sc., F.N.I., Director Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi for his keen interest and valuable suggestion in connection with this piece of work.

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY,
JADAVPUR, CALCUTTA
AND
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

Received November 4, 1948.

INDIAN ASSOCIATION FOR THE CULTIVATION OF SCIENCE

210, BOWBAZAR STREET, CALCUTTA—12.

Applications are invited for the post of Professor of Organic Chemistry in the grade Rs. 800-40-1000; 1000-50-1250.

Applicants should be distinguished scientists having long experience of research—specially of work in high polymers and should be qualified to organise and promote research and guide scholars.

Six copies of applications together with testimonials, statement of qualifications and age, and copies of original publications, should reach the Registrar on or before July 15, 1949.

For candidates applying from overseas, abstracts of applications may be sent in advance by Air Mail on or before August 15, 1949.